

Project Title **Implementing FAIR Workflows: a proof of concept study in the field of consciousness**

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D4.4 Open Source Code and Documentation

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Project summary

The implementing FAIR Workflows project aims to provide an exemplar workflow throughout the research project lifecycle. Leveraging existing open scholarly infrastructure, particularly persistent identifier (PID) systems and open metadata, the goal of the project is to make the research process open, results reproducible, and outputs findable, accessible, interoperable, and ultimately reusable for the scholarly community and wider society. Through a collaboration with researchers and multiple partner organizations, the project addresses workflows for research funders, service integrators, and researchers, to actively incorporate PID and metadata creation and management processes, and provides detailed specifications and recommendation documents to support the practical implementation.

Executive summary

This deliverable provides the documentation that accompanies the project dashboard developed within the FAIR Workflows project. The dashboard is an integrated part of the project that aims to drive the adoption of open and FAIR research practices among researchers and advance wider integration of open infrastructure among research supporting tools and services. Hosted on DataCite Commons, it provides an at-a-glance view of the key information about a research project derived from its DOI metadata, including but not limited to the people, institutions, funders, and related outputs. The dashboard is developed as an open source project, with all modules openly accessible and forkable on GitHub. We provide thorough user documentation on the Support site describing the different features.

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Introduction

This document consists of the technical and user documentation of the project dashboard¹. The technical documentation is intended for developers and open source contributors to easily find and understand the open source code behind the dashboard, and provide pointers for the technical community to reuse, contribute to, and maintain the codebase. The user documentation provides all the information users need to navigate and use the dashboard and is published on the DataCite Support site² for accessibility and easy reference.

Technical Documentation

The project dashboard on DataCite Commons collects, arranges, and displays information about a research project, based on the DOI metadata of the project and its related entities, including researchers, research organizations, funding, and related works. The dashboard is supported by the the DataCite REST API and GraphQL API³ as the backend, and uses NextJS and react components to organize and present the data. The following are the details of each of the components.

Code for dashboard Components

- Works Dashboard
 - <https://github.com/datacite/akita/blob/d5861baf501703f04cb7e4f63d2b00d67f74c1ee/src/components/WorksDashboard/WorksDashboard.tsx>
- Works Listing
 - <https://github.com/datacite/akita/blob/d5861baf501703f04cb7e4f63d2b00d67f74c1ee/src/components/WorksListing/WorksListing.tsx>
- Sankey chart
 - <https://github.com/datacite/akita/tree/d5861baf501703f04cb7e4f63d2b00d67f74c1ee/src/components/SankeyGraph>

¹Chen, X., Cousijn, H., & Stathis, K. (2024). Implementing FAIR Workflows D3.1 Track Connections with the Project Dashboard. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10727214>

²<https://support.datacite.org/docs/projects-in-datacite-commons>

³Fenner, M. (2020). *Powering the PID Graph: Announcing the DataCite GraphQL API*. <https://doi.org/10.5438/YFCK-MV39>

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- <https://github.com/datacite/akita/blob/d5861baf501703f04cb7e4f63d2b00d67f74c1ee/src/components/WorksListing/WorksListing.tsx#L79>
- Example input (see section below)
- Force directed graph
 - <https://github.com/datacite/akita/tree/583e2ccf02df89299d5e8b91d2ab2b53c83ff600/src/components/ForceDirectedGraph>
 - Example input (see section below)
- Horizontal bar chart
 - Horizontal bar chart folder:
<https://github.com/datacite/akita/tree/d5861baf501703f04cb7e4f63d2b00d67f74c1ee/src/components/HorizontalStackedBarChart>
 - Example implementation of Horizontal bar chart:
<https://github.com/datacite/akita/blob/d5861baf501703f04cb7e4f63d2b00d67f74c1ee/src/components/WorksDashboard/WorksDashboard.tsx#L44>
- Related Works CSV Download
 - NextJS API route and GraphQL endpoint for data organization to support csv download:
<https://github.com/datacite/akita/blob/d5861baf501703f04cb7e4f63d2b00d67f74c1ee/src/app/api/download-reports/doi/related-works/route.ts>

Libraries used

- Vega <https://vega.github.io/vega/>
- Vega-lite <https://vega.github.io/vega-lite/>
- React-vega <https://github.com/vega/react-vega>
- Csv-stringify <https://csv.js.org/stringify/>

Example input data

EXAMPLE FOR SANKEY GRAPH

[

```
{ data: ["Erin Robinson", "Project Leader", "Audiovisual"], count: 7 },
{ data: ["Neil Davies", "Creator", "Audiovisual"], count: 4 },
{ data: ["Maria Praetzellis", "Project Leader", "Audiovisual"], count: 8 },
{ data: ["Maria Praetzellis", "Creator", "Software"], count: 6 },
{ data: ["Brian Riley", "Data Curator", "Dataset"], count: 3 },
{ data: ["Brian Riley", "Creator", "Dataset"], count: 9 }
]
```

EXAMPLE FOR FORCE DIRECTED GRAPH

```
export const TEST_NODES: ForceDirectedGraphNode[] = [
  { title: 'Preprint', count: 22357 },
  { title: 'Software', count: 136204 },
  { title: 'Dataset', count: 7524645 },
  { title: 'Organization', count: 97795 },
  { title: 'Journal Article', count: 14043135 },
  { title: 'Person', count: 8718993 }
]

export const TEST_LINKS: ForceDirectedGraphLink[] = [
  { source: 'Preprint', target: 'Software', count: 7992 },
  { source: 'Preprint', target: 'Dataset', count: 68292 },
  { source: 'Preprint', target: 'Journal Article', count: 25263 },

  { source: 'Software', target: 'Dataset', count: 1983 },
  { source: 'Software', target: 'Person', count: 28612 },
  { source: 'Software', target: 'Organization', count: 24 },

  { source: 'Dataset', target: 'Organization', count: 11657 },
  { source: 'Dataset', target: 'Person', count: 546454 },
  { source: 'Dataset', target: 'Journal Article', count: 387906 },

  { source: 'Organization', target: 'Journal Article', count: 1777 },
  { source: 'Organization', target: 'Person', count: 3009 },

  { source: 'Journal Article', target: 'Person', count: 3847926 },
  { source: 'Journal Article', target: 'Journal Article', count: 2043502 }
]
```


Contribution and feedback

We encourage the community to directly engage with and contribute to the corpus of open source code behind the applications offered by DataCite, including but not limited to the components used in the dashboard - the dashboard is embedded to the DataCite Commons general structure, any change could easily go beyond the scope of just the project dashboard.

There are three ways one can work with the open source code:

- Directly contribute to the code base. To do this, please follow the steps below and comply to general GitHub community guidelines⁴:
 - Fork the project
 - Write tests for your new feature or a test that reproduces a bug
 - Implement your feature or make a bug fix
 - Commit, push and make a pull request
- Submitting ideas to improve the dashboard to the DataCite public roadmap <https://datacite.org/roadmap/>
- Create your application reusing DataCite code. When you do this, please add the DataCite topic to the repository <https://support.datacite.org/docs/code-examples-on-github>

⁴ <https://docs.github.com/en/site-policy/github-terms/github-community-guidelines>

User documentation

Projects in DataCite Commons

When a DataCite DOI has "Project" as "resourceType", in combination with "Text" or "Other" as "resourceTypeGeneral" in the metadata, it is recognized as a project and the record will be presented on DataCite Commons in the form of a project dashboard.

Search projects

Use the Works tab in DataCite Commons to search the metadata catalog of all DataCite DOIs in Findable state, including DOIs for projects. To start, enter a search term or query in the search bar at the top of the page.

Project facets

On the search result page, check the "Project" check box in the "Work Type" facets on the left column to see all search term related projects.

The "Work Type" section contains the top 10 most frequent resource types in the result, so it's possible that "Project" falls out of scope. In this case, use [advanced search queries](#) to find DOIs based on the resource type.

Work Type	
<input type="checkbox"/> Study Registration	113,380
<input type="checkbox"/> Text	22,473
<input type="checkbox"/> Project	16,186
<input type="checkbox"/> Dataset	439
<input type="checkbox"/> Journal Article	435
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	132
<input type="checkbox"/> Collection	80
<input type="checkbox"/> Dissertation	71
<input type="checkbox"/> Preprint	69
<input type="checkbox"/> Report	46

Open Search query

To find all DOIs registered for projects, use the REST API querying parameter “types.resourceType” in combination with “types.resourceTypeGeneral” to define search. For a full list of parameters, please see the [API Reference](#).

- To find projects with resourceTypeGeneral “Text” or “Other”
 - <https://commons.datacite.org/?query=types.resourceTypeGeneral%3AOther+OR+types.resourceTypeGeneral%3AText+AND+types.resourceType%3AProject>
- Alternatively, one can simply use “project” as the resource type parameter in the search query
 - https://commons.datacite.org/doi.org?query=*%&resource-type=project

The screenshot shows the DataCite Commons search results page. The search bar contains the query: `types.resourceTypeGeneral:Text AND types.resourceType:Project`. The results show 78,995 Works. The page is divided into several sections:

- Creators & Contributors**: A list of creators with their respective work counts.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Feldman, Gilad	203
<input type="checkbox"/>	Mckenna, Amy	156
<input type="checkbox"/>	Gomeseria, Ronald Valledor	137
<input type="checkbox"/>	Gomeseria, Ronald Valledor	137
<input type="checkbox"/>	Youngstrom, Eric	130
<input type="checkbox"/>	陈, 子俊	111
<input type="checkbox"/>	Soares, Roniere	109
<input type="checkbox"/>	van Veenendaal, Remco	97
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hidayat, Atep	96
<input type="checkbox"/>	Siahaan, Andysah	90
- Publication Year**: A list of years with their respective work counts.

<input type="checkbox"/>	2024	6,938
<input type="checkbox"/>	2023	13,484
<input type="checkbox"/>	2022	55,657
<input type="checkbox"/>	2021	1,355
<input type="checkbox"/>	2020	800
<input type="checkbox"/>	2019	368
<input type="checkbox"/>	2018	195
<input type="checkbox"/>	2017	146
<input type="checkbox"/>	2016	35
<input type="checkbox"/>	2015	11
<input type="checkbox"/>	2014	1
<input type="checkbox"/>	2013	4
<input type="checkbox"/>	2012	1
- Work Type**: A list of work types with their respective counts.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Project	78,995
--------------------------	---------	--------

The main content area displays three search results, each with a "Text" button and a DOI link:

- Supporting information for 'Flexible parental care: Uniparental incubation in biparentally incubating shorebirds'**
 Martin Bulla
 Project published 2022 in Open Science Framework
 Original study
 DOI registered September 17, 2016 via DataCite.
 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/osf.io/3rsny>
- Prediction errors but not sharpened signals simulate multivoxel fMRI patterns during speech perception**
 Helen Blank
 Project published 2022 in Open Science Framework
 DOI registered September 17, 2016 via DataCite.
 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/osf.io/2ze9n>
- Lab Experiments for the Study of Social-Ecological Systems Supplementary Materials**
 Marco Janssen, Robert Holahan, Allen Lee & Elinor Ostrom
 Project published 2022 in Open Science Framework
 Datasets, archived configuration files, and Dockerized experiment software bundle used in <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1183532>
 DOI registered September 17, 2016 via DataCite.
 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/osf.io/mdhb7>

More about using [boolean operators in search queries](#).

The project record

The project dashboard page retains the [features of the DOI record page of other work types](#), and provides a number of added features specific for projects.

Download Reports

This feature adds a link to the dashboard, allowing users to download a .csv file containing a list of all Related Works. The list includes descriptions and formatted citations in APA style for up to 200 DOIs associated with the project.

ID Add to ORCID Record

Download Metadata

Cite as

Cousijn, H., & Melloni, L. (2021). *Implementing FAIR Workflows: A Proof of Concept Study in the Field of Consciousness*. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.60581/ZAEV-6P15>

APA

Download Reports

Related Works (CSV) ?

Share

Title	Publication	DOI	Description	Formatted	Resource T	Resource T	Connection	Type
Domain-sp	2024	10.60745/k2wv-x835	Zefan Zhen	Other	Template		Other Relation	
Implementi	2024	10.5281/zeThe	Chen, X.,	C Report			Other Relation	
Implemetin	2024	10.5281/zeThe	Chen, X.,	C Text		Project deli	Other Relation	
Implementi	2024	10.5281/zeThe	Chen, X.,	C Report			Other Relation	
Guide for R	2024	10.5281/ze Convention	Chen, X.,	C Text		Project deli	Other Relation	
Guide for R	2024	10.5281/ze Convention	Chen, X.,	C Text		Project deli	Other Relation	
Guide for fu	2023	10.5281/zeThis	Chen, X.,	C Report			Reference	
Implementi	2023	10.5438/8c Implement	Praetzellis,	Text	blog post		Reference	
Making Res	2023	10.2218/ec Persistent i	Chen, X. (2)	JournalArtic	JournalArtic		Reference	
Making Res	2023	10.2218/ec Persistent i	Chen, X. (2)	JournalArtic	JournalArtic		Reference	
FAIR Workfl	2023	10.48321/c The Implerr	Chen, X. (2)	OutputMan	Data Manag		Citation	
Final Pre-re	2023	10.17605/c The	TrÁ¼butscf	StudyRegis	Pre-registrz	Part		
Implementi	2023	10.5281/zeThe	Chen, X.,	C Report			Other Relation	
Implementi	2023	10.5281/zeThe Implerr	Chen, X.,	M Text	Project deli		Other Relation	
Implementi	2023	10.5281/zeThe	Borup, N.,	C Report			Other Relation	
Implementi	2023	10.5281/zeThe	Borup, N.,	C Report			Other Relation	
Replicating	2023	10.5061/dr Attribute	Zheng, Z.,	8 Dataset	dataset		Other Relation	
Replicating	2023	10.5281/ze Attribute Ar	Zheng, Z.,	8 Software			Other Relation	
Replicating	2023	10.5281/ze Attribute Ar	Zheng, Z.,	8 Software			Other Relation	
Replicating	2023	10.5281/ze Attribute Ar	Zheng, Z.,	8 Other			Other Relation	
Replicating	2023	10.5281/ze Attribute Ar	Zheng, Z.,	8 Other			Other Relation	
Implementi	2022	10.5281/ze The Implerr	Chen, X. (2)	Text	Project deli		Reference	
Implementi	2022	10.5281/ze The Implerr	Chen, X.,	C Text	Project deli		Reference	
The pitfalls	2022	10.5438/8t Implement	Zheng, Z.,	8 Text	blog post		Reference	
FAIR is ever	2022	10.5438/9g5c-4037	Cousijn, H.	Text	blog post		Reference	
Implementi	2022	10.5281/ze Researche	Chen, X.,	C Report			Reference	
Mind the ga	2022	10.5438/nf Implement	Chen, X. Mi	Text	blog post		Reference	
Replicating	2022	10.17605/c Attribute	Melloni, L.,	StudyRegis	Pre-registrz	Part		
Re-replicati	2022	10.17605/c In the	Zheng, Z.,	8 StudyRegis	Pre-registrz	Part		
Testing Attr	2022	10.17605/c We embedc	Zheng, Z. (2)	StudyRegis	Pre-registrz	Part		
Using Attrib	2022	10.17605/c This projec	TrÁ¼butscf	Text	Project	Part		

Network Graph

This feature implementation generates a force-directed graph that shows a high-level overview of the different types of shared works connected to a Project and the number of connections between them. This visualization is based on the resource types and related identifiers of the DOIs in the Related Works section identifier metadata.

Related Works List and Connection Type Facets

The Related Works list contains all works that are associated with the project DOI in the metadata, sorted into the following bins (shown as facets in the left column): “All”, “Citations”, “References”, “Parts”, “Is Part Of”, and “Other”. “All” and “Other” are implemented as a new subcategories - “All” surfaces all registered works that are related to the project through related identifier metadata regardless of connection type, while “Other” filters related works that are linked through related identifier metadata with connection types⁵ that are allowed in the “relationtype” metadata field,

⁵ <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.5/appendices/appendix-1/relationType/>

aside from "Citations", "References", "Parts" and "Is Part Of".

Filter Works

Type to search...

Connection Types

- All 31
- References 10
- Citations 1
- Parts 5
- Other 15

Creators & Contributors ?

- Zheng, Zefan 11
- Lucia Melloni 7
- Chen, Xiaoli 7
- Cousijn, Helena 5
- Trübutschek, Darinka 4
- Brown, Tanya 3
- Stathis, Kelly 2
- Praetzelis, Maria 1
- Graybeal, John 1
- Pfeiffer, Nicole 1

Publication Year

- 2024 6
- 2023 15
- 2022 10

Work Type

- Text 10
- Report 7
- Study Registration 4
- Other 3
- Journal Article 2
- Software 2
- Dataset 1
- Output Management Plan 1
- Project 1

License

- CC-BY-4.0 22
- CC-BY-SA-4.0 6

Related Works

Publication Year

Work Types

Text 32%

Licenses

CC-BY-4.0 71%

Contributions to All Related Works ?

Replicating Attribute Amnesia Effect in the Single-Stimulus Design

Lucia Melloni, Darinka Trübutschek, Xiaoli Chen & Zefan Zheng
Pre Registration published 2022 in Open Science Framework

Attribute Amnesia refers to the phenomenon that subjects fail to report some features (e.g., colour) of a stimulus after they have been asked to repetitively report some other features (e.g., numeric parity) of the same stimulus (Chen & Wyble, 2015). This effect has shown strong replicability in the multi-stimuli design, in which there are normally one target among three distractors stimuli. Recently, Wang et al. (2021) furtherly showed the robustness of this effect when there was only one stimulus on the screen. As the main experiment of the current project will be conducted online, we aim to pre-register replication attempt of Experiment 1 of Wang et al. (2021) in the online-experiment setting. Chen, H., & Wyble, B. (2015). Amnesia for object attributes: Failure to report attended information that had just reached conscious awareness. *Psychological science*, 26(2), 203-210. Wang, R., Fu, Y., Chen, L., Chen, Y., Zhou, J., & Chen, H. (2021). Consciousness can overflow report: novel evidence from attribute amnesia of a single stimulus. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 87, 103052.

Other Identifiers
 URL: <https://osf.io/4nf7q>
 DOI registered January 25, 2022 via DataCite.

1 Citation

[Study Registration](#) [Psychology](#)

<https://doi.org/10.17605/osf.io/4nf7q>

Re-replicating Attribute Amnesia Effect Using Single-Stimulus Design after Minor

Contributions chart

This feature showcases the top contributors to the project and how they contributed to the main types of outputs of the project. The Sankey chart shows two columns: person on the left, work-type on the right. It visualizes the number of times each person is associated with each work type.

Acknowledgement

The project dashboard is developed as part of the [Implementing FAIR Workflows project](#) funded by the [Templeton World Charity Foundation](#).

This project was made possible through the support of a grant from Templeton World Charity Foundation, Inc. The opinions expressed in this publication are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of Templeton World Charity Foundation, Inc.

Summary

Providing an easy and intuitive way to demonstrate the insights held in open metadata is important as it surfaces the value of open infrastructure which is often hidden away. The dashboard consolidates a number of most needed features and visualizations to support use cases like reporting, showcasing, and evaluation. With the documentation, we invite the community to test,

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use, and more importantly, engage with the continued betterment of the dashboard and DataCite Commons, either through providing feedback, or developing new features to further support the adoption of open infrastructure, and FAIR workflows.